

STUDY AND SIMULATION OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF ORGANIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Several studies have been carried out on weight saving on structural equipments. Now research focuses on onboard equipments. Those equipments in contact with electrical components need to be thermally conductive in order to enable the cool down of the electronic devices. This work is a part of our on-going research in the frame of the THEOREM project (THERmal Organic Enhanced Materials). This project led by THALES Systèmes Aéroportés aims to develop a hybrid composite material made of a polymeric matrix filled with micro and nanoparticles exhibiting a high thermal conductivity and reinforced with long carbon fibres (PITCH fibres). This material should exhibit high thermal conductivity.

To define the effective thermal properties of composites two main lines are developed.

The first one concerns the improvement of thermal conductivity of a thermoset matrix by addition of different kinds of fillers. A numerical model of this filled matrix was developed to obtain homogenised properties.

The second one is about the improvement of heat transfer of the whole material by carbon fibre reinforcements in the three directions of space. Homogenised properties of the filled matrix were then used at the mesoscopic scale taking into account geometric models of reinforcements such as plain-weave or 2.5D interlocks. Effective properties of composite are determined by gathering of those two studies (fig.1).

2 Filled matrix

2.1 Aim

Within the frame of THEOREM project, our main task was to develop a numerical tool enabling both:

- On a micromechanical scale: the prediction of thermal and mechanical properties of filled matrices.

- On a macromechanical scale: the prediction of the same properties of a composite reinforced with carbon fibres.

This study is made on COMSOL Multiphysics 4.3.b. Within the framework of THEOREM project, we also have to take into account industrial processes technologies and particle dispersion methods in liquid state resin. Those dispersion methods involve a random locating of particles.

2.1.1 Algorithm

First study was made on spherical particles with same diameter and randomly dispersed in a representative volume element (RVE). The algorithm of particles generation is shown in figure 2.

To this end a random function is used to generate points considered as particles centres. A non-penetration parameter which allows only contacts between spheres was determined.

2.1.2 RVE and mesh size

Since the filled matrix does not exist, it is impossible to determine the dimension of the RVE from micrographies of the material as made in most of studies. Here the size of the RVE is decided as a function of fillers sizes. Nevertheless fillers size is not a sufficient information to decide the dimensions of a cubic RVE. The achievable particle volume fractions are also a key parameter for determining the RVE dimensions. For example if one sphere of 6 μm of diameter is placed in a cubic RVE, which the length edge L depends on the particles volume fraction v_p , we have for $v_p = 3\%$ $L = 15.56 \mu\text{m}$, for $v_p = 30\%$ $L = 7.22 \mu\text{m}$, for $v_p = 50\%$ $L = 6.09 \mu\text{m}$.

To study the influence of the length edge of the RVE on the thermal conductivity coefficient, the size of edges of the cubic RVE was ranged between 25 μm and 100 μm . Average radius of particles was set at 3 μm and volume fraction (v_p) at 3 %. Mesh size was also studied in parallel. An average volume per

element was defined. This parameter is determined by the total volume of the model divided by the total number of mesh elements (tetrahedral elements in our case). Coarser is the mesh size higher is this parameter.

Figure 3 highlights the influence of RVE size on thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of mesh size (average volume per element). In this way, on models with a RVE of 100 μm edge, a decrease of thermal conductivity coefficient was observed between 5 and 10 μm^3 , which corresponds to a mesh ranging from 100,000 to 210,000 elements. In order to remain in the stabilized part of the curve, i.e. an average volume per element of 5 μm^3 , mesh size need to be refined, thus increase of time calculations. It seems that a RVE of 100 μm edge is not the best compromise. Moreover figure 3 shows a case with low particle volume fractions; new models with high particle volume fractions will exponentially increase time calculations. On the opposite, models with a RVE of 25 μm edge involve an extremely coarser mesh that can lead to deformed elements, compromising the good resolution of the model. Indeed an average volume per element of 8 μm^3 matches with a model of 2,000 elements. The best compromise between mesh size and time calculation remains a RVE of 50 μm edge.

2.1.3 Random distribution interest

The aim of this part was to highlighted differences between a random distribution and a periodic arrangement of particles which is in fact experimentally unachievable. Those different arrangements were simulated on COMSOL Multiphysics. The thermal conductivity coefficient was determined owing to the Fourier's law expressed on equation (1). Figure 4 shows that thermal conductivity coefficient is not influenced by the axis used for boundary conditions defined in the next section. Moreover only conduction phenomenon was considered. So it could be considered that the doped matrix is an isotropic material and Fourier's law can be applied.

$$\phi = -\lambda \overrightarrow{\text{grad}} T \quad (1)$$

For example tab. 1 illustrate the effect of the layout on thermal conductivity coefficient for a particle volume fraction $v_p = 3\%$. L represents the edge length of RVE. In order to compare those models at iso volume fraction (here v_p was set at 3% vol.), RVE size was adjusted in the case of pseudo body centered cubic (Figure 5) and pseudo face centered cubic (Figure 6) models.

Figure 7 illustrates the case of all particles located on one faces and figure 8 the case of all particles distributed between both faces in the heat flux direction.

Tab. 1 shows that thermal behaviour of cases 1, 3 and 4 give similar results of thermal conductivity coefficient. Then cases 2 and 5 point out that thermal conductivity coefficient is twice as large as other models. Case 2 does not correspond to any material reality and case 5 highlights that if all particles are adjoined between them they create a favourite path for heat flux. However this case does not seem feasible.

2.1.4 Changes in thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of particles volume fraction

To study the influence of particle volume fraction on the thermal conductivity coefficient of filled matrix, following boundary conditions were applied (Figure 9):

- Cubic RVE edge length: $L = 50 \mu\text{m}$
- Thermal conductivity coefficient of matrix: $\lambda_m = 0.2 \text{ W}/(\text{m.K})$
- Thermal conductivity coefficient of fillers: $\lambda_p = 237 \text{ W}/(\text{m.K})$ (aluminium particles)
- Radius fillers: $R = 3 \mu\text{m}$
- Initial temperature: $T_0 = 0 \text{ K}$
- Surface heat flux: $\Phi_S = 1 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$

Those boundary conditions allow simplifications on the resolution of Fourier law.

Figure 10 shows the changes in thermal conductivity coefficient in the case of a RVE of 50 μm edge and for an average radius of particles of 3 μm . Thus an increase in the thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of particle volume fractions ($v_p\%$) was observed. However a numerical limitation of the model due to capabilities of the PC used in this work was highlighted. Indeed beyond 20% of particles in volume, meshing becomes impossible with PC assigned to this project (16 Go RAM, 8 cores at 1.87 GHz).

2.1.5 Particles diameter effect

It is well-known that real filler size is not at all a single and constant value. Usually when a micronic or submicronic size filler is considered, the particles real dimensions follow a Gaussian distribution. An important assumption of our study is that all the fillers have the same dimensions. This is a rough assumption but it enables to perform first computations. However, it is planned to take into consideration a Gaussian distribution of particles dimensions within a very near future.

Figure 11 highlights particle size effect on thermal conductivity coefficient in the case of a RVE of 50 μm edge, an average radius of 1 or 3 μm et for $v_p = 3\%$. Because of the particle size, models corresponding to an average radius of 1 μm have a smaller average volume per element and a decrease of thermal conductivity coefficient previously observed occurs earlier than with models using an average radius of 3 μm . However if this part of the curve is not taken into account, values of thermal conductivity coefficients between models with a radius of 1 or 3 μm are the same. Thus in order to limit computation time it is better to chose an average radius of 3 μm .

2.1.6 Summarize of numerical modelling

In summarize the choice in the RVE size is made by compromise between mesh size and calculation speed. In this way we noticed the best compromise was a RVE size of 50 μm . The distribution of particle sizes is not still taking into account in this model. In order to verify a potential effect of particle size, a variation between two values of average radius highlights that a too small particle size compare to RVE size causes an increase of mesh element numbers, thus an increase of time calculation.

2.2 Analytical models

The interest of analytical models available in literature is found in their quick estimation of thermal conductivity coefficient.

2.2.1 Definition of models

In a first time, in order to correlate with numerical model previously develop, we focalised on analytical models adapted to spherical particles. Thermal conductivity models could be divided in two groups: those considering a perfect particles/matrix interface and those considering this interface as imperfect. In this case this mean that it has to take into account a thermal contact resistance between components; particles and polymer matrix.

In the case of a perfect interface we targeted the following models: effective medium model [1], Hamilton-Crosser model [2], Lewis-Nielsen model [3].

In the case of imperfect interface we limited to Hasselman and Johnson model [4]. For all models describe hereinafter λ_c the thermal conductivity coefficient of composite, λ_m the thermal conductivity coefficient of matrix, λ_p the thermal conductivity

coefficient of particles and v_p the particle volume fraction.

Effective medium model (equation (2)) is valid for low particle volume fractions.

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_m \left[1 + \frac{3v_p \left(\frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} - 1 \right)}{\left(\frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} + 2 \right) - v_p \left(\frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} - 1 \right)} \right] \quad (2)$$

Hamilton-Crosser model (equation (3)), depends on a shape factor n which take into account particle geometry. n factor define the particle sphericity (equation (3)). For spherical particles $n = 3$.

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_m \left[\frac{\lambda_p + (n-1)\lambda_m - (n-1)v_p(\lambda_m - \lambda_p)}{\lambda_p + (n-1)\lambda_m + v_p(\lambda_m - \lambda_p)} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$n = \frac{3}{\psi} \quad (4)$$

With ψ the particle sphericity

$$\psi = \frac{Surf_{sph}}{Surf_{part}} \quad (5)$$

With $Surf_{sph}$, the surface of a sphere having the same volume as the particle and $Surf_{part}$, the surface of the particle.

Lewis-Nielsen model (equation (6)) takes into account the maximum packing fraction Φ_m , as well as a parameter A (equation (7)) depending on the Einstein generalized coefficient k_E . This parameter is function of the pure matrix viscosity, the doped matrix viscosity and the particle volume fraction. It assumes that for spherical microparticles $k_E = 2.5$ and for prolate or oblate ellipsoid microparticles k_E is higher than 2.5 [5].

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_m \left(\frac{1 + ABv_p}{1 - Bv_p\psi} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$B = \frac{\frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} - 1}{\frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} + A}$$

$$\psi = 1 + \left(\frac{1 - \Phi_m}{\Phi_m^2} \right) v_p$$

$$A = k_E - 1 \quad (7)$$

In the case of a random packing of spherical particles $A = 1.5$ and $\Phi_m = 0.637$. This model takes

into account the geometric aspect of particles and their distribution in the matrix.

Hasselman and Johnson model (equation(8)), takes into account an imperfect particles/matrix interface. It depends on, besides parameters previously define, the particle radius a and the thermal conductance h_c which represents the interface thermal resistance.

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_m \frac{2 \left(\frac{\lambda_m}{\lambda_p} - \frac{\lambda_p}{ah_c} - 1 \right) v_p + \frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} + \frac{2\lambda_p}{ah_c} + 2}{\left(1 - \frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} + \frac{\lambda_p}{ah_c} \right) v_p + \frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_m} + \frac{2\lambda_p}{ah_c} + 2} \quad (8)$$

2.2.2 Analytical results

To compare different analytical values of thermal conductivity coefficient of composite in function of particle volume fraction (v_p), thermal conductivity coefficient of matrix is set at $\lambda_m = 0.2$ W/(m.K) (general value of epoxy systems), whereas thermal conductivity coefficient of particles (here aluminium) is set at $\lambda_p = 237$ W/(m.K). Average radius of particles was considered constant: $a = 3$ μ m. Particle volume fraction v_p ranges between 0% and 55%. For Hasselman model, the thermal boundary conductance h_c depends on matrix, particles and interface geometry. It is quite difficult to define an exact value, h_c value is thus determined according to [1] $h_c = 1.10^{-7}$ W/K.

Figure 12 results show that effective medium model and Hasselman model exhibit the same trends. Hamilton model is close to Hasselman model. Lewis-Nielsen model is limited to a maximum value of packing fraction of particles which is 63.7% in our case. Numerical results are between Hasselman and Hamilton models. Hasselman model depends on h_c parameter which is difficult to determine experimentally or numerically. Hamilton depends on the n parameter which employs particle sphericity. Thus it is possible to observe the effect of shape particle on the model. Hamilton model is thus defined as referential analytical model.

2.3 Experiment

2.3.1 Components

Two groups of samples are made. The first one in Institut Clément Ader (ICA) with an epoxy system MAP R.12.13.03.i1 doped with 11HPS aluminium particles (Toyal) and copper particles (Pometon). The second one was produce in RESCOLL (project partner) with an epoxy system LY556 + D230 (Hunstman) doped with Z600 aluminium particles (Toyal). Fillers were dispersed using a pale mixer then masterbatches were put on moulds and cured in

an oven. Z600 particles have $d(50) = 6.484$ μ m and 11HPS particles have $d(50) = 9.752$ μ m. Figure 13 is an optical microscope observation of the distribution of Z600 aluminium and copper particles for different volume fractions. ImageJ was used to analyse those images as shown in Figure 14. Original images were 256 greyscale images. To analyse the particle contours a binarization in black and white and then a manual thresholding (operator dependent) were made. The shape of Z600 aluminium particles is close to circle, thus we could consider that this shape approach a sphere shape, whereas copper particles come close to needle shape. For aluminium particles, for $v_p = 50\%$, it could be also observe an agglomerate creation.

2.3.2 Measurements

Density values are determined by immersion weighing method, specific heat capacity values are experimentally obtained by DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry). Values of thermal conductivity coefficient at room temperature are determined by equation (9) based on diffusivity measurements made on a Nanoflash LFA 447 (NETZSCH) for RESCOLL samples and on a Microflash LFA 457 (NETZSCH) for ICA samples. Those values are listed on Tab. 2.

$$\lambda = aC_p\rho \quad (9)$$

with λ , a , C_p and ρ respectively thermal conductivity coefficient, thermal diffusivity, specific heat capacity and density of the sample.

2.3.3 Comparison between experimental results and analytical and numerical models

Values of thermal conductivity coefficient of analytical and numerical models and experimental results are compared figure 15. Both models underestimate the value of experimental thermal conductivity coefficient. However, as underlined on 2.2.2, Hamilton model depends on a parameter n which takes into account shape particles. In figures 16, 17 and 18 obtained results highlight the effect of this parameter on Hamilton model knowing that for spherical particles $n = 3$. Thus, the geometry of Z600 aluminium particles is close to the one of a sphere seeing that experimental results are surrounded by n values between 3.6 and 4.4. On the other hand, the geometry of 11 HPS aluminium particles and copper particles move away from the geometry of a sphere. Those observations are in agreement with figures 13 and 14, pictures showing epoxy/copper microstructure. In conclusion higher is the value of n

more the sphere becomes a prolate ellipsoid or a very flat plate. So, figures 16 to 18 highlight the influence of particle shape on the thermal conductivity coefficient of a doped matrix. For example for matrix doped with copper particles ($\lambda_m = 0.145$ W/(m.K) and $\lambda_p = 385$ W/(m.K)) (figure 18), for a particle volume fraction $v_p = 15\%$, for $n = 3$ (spherical particles) $\lambda_c = 0.2472$ W/(m.K) whereas for $n = 9$, $\lambda_c = 0.4$ W/(m.K) meaning an increase of 61.8%, or for $n = 18$, $\lambda_c = 0.6262$ W/(m.K) corresponding to an increase of 153.3% compare to $n = 3$. Finally the more particle shape comes close to needle shape the more the thermal conductivity coefficient of the doped matrix increase.

3 Reinforcements: numerical modelling

Mesoscopic scale was investigated from an experimental, an analytical and a numerical point of view. Reinforcements studied are 2D, 2.5D Interlock and orthogonal 3D. They are developed by an industrial partner of the project. From a numerical modelling point of view, initially we have created representative numerical models of different fibrous structures used in this project, in order to study their thermal behaviour. The aim of this study was to analyse the effect of the fibre volume fraction on thermal conductivity coefficient of an epoxy/carbonate fibres composite. Indeed, in manufacturing of laminated composite parts by liquid moulding process, the thickness of the part, thus plies of fibres and matrix interplies, depends on process parameters – closing pressure of the mould. In the end fibre volume fraction increases with laminate crushing and this fact certainly influence the transverse thermal conductivity coefficient of the laminate. A numerical modelling by finite element method was developed with ABAQUS. RVE is defined as shown in figure 19. The thermal conductivity coefficient of the matrix is defined isotropic and the one of the fibre as orthotropic. The value of the longitudinal thermal conductivity coefficient of fibres is given by supplier data for NGF (Nippon Graphite Fiber Corp.) XN90 (PITCH) fibres. The value of transverse thermal conductivity coefficient is supposed set at 1/3 or 1/10 of the value of longitudinal thermal conductivity coefficient (Tab.3) as hypothesized in literature [6].

Fibre thickness remains constant throughout the study ($e = 1$ mm). Resin thickness on upper and lower faces of RVE as well as interface between fibres, range between 0 mm (perfect contact) and

1 mm (fibre thickness). Fibre volume fraction v_f range between 25% and 62.5%. A temperature delta of 10K was applied between upper and lower faces of the model perpendicular to the lamination plane.

Figure 20 highlights the heat flux distribution perpendicular to the lamination plane for a volume fraction of 25% (resin interface of 1mm between fibres) and 62.5% (no interface between fibres). It is clearly observed that the heat flux is lower in the model with $v_f = 25\%$. In order to evaluate transverse thermal conductivity coefficient of the model, the heat flux was calculated on upper and lower faces of RVE and the thermal conductivity coefficient was determined by equation(10).

$$\lambda_{te} = \frac{\Phi e_{layer}}{\Delta T} \quad (10)$$

with λ_{te} , the effective transverse thermal conductivity coefficient of composite, Φ , the heat flux, e_{layer} , the composite thickness, ΔT the temperature delta set between both faces of composite.

Figure 21 illustrates the evolution of thermal conductivity coefficient of the composite in function of fibre volume fraction for both values of transverse conductivity ($\lambda_{t1} = 60$ W/(m.K) and $\lambda_{t2} = 200$ W/(m.K)). Results show that an increase of fibre volume fraction involves an increase of thermal conductivity. Also an increase in the value of transverse thermal conductivity coefficient of fibres involves an increase in the effective transverse thermal conductivity coefficient. Finally, to simulate a doped resin, the thermal conductivity coefficient of the resin is multiplied by 3 (from 0.2 to 0.6 W/(m.K)), the effective thermal conductivity of the composite change from 7.75 W/(m.K) to 16.2 W/(m.K) for $v_f = 61.6\%$.

4 Conclusion – In prospect

A numerical model allowing to randomly dispersed spheres on a RVE was developed. This 3D model is able to define the homogenized value of thermal conductivity coefficient of a doped matrix as a function of particle volume fraction. This homogenized value is used on the determination of thermal conductivity coefficient of a hybrid composite constituted by a doped matrix and reinforced with long carbon fibres. A numerical limitation was highlighted from $v_p = 20\%$ but it is not problematic according to previous comment. Optical microscope observations show that some particle geometries are closer to a deformed ellipsoid

than a sphere. This was correlated with Hamilton model which highlighted the effect of particle sphericity on thermal conductivity coefficient. A new numerical model generating random distribution of ellipsoidal particles is in progress. For reinforcements, simple structures were investigated first. A study on plain-weave compaction was led to observe effect of fibre volume fraction on thermal conductivity coefficient. New studies on satin-5 and Interlock 2.5D are in progress. RVE models of composite with homogenized matrix suppose there is no resin in fibres. A thought on the validity of this assumption is still in progress, with the development of an experimental device enabling the thermal conductivity coefficient on dry or impregnated fibres to be measured.

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Fig. 1. Numerical modelling approach. Doped matrix: COMSOL Multiphysics, textile: ABAQUS.

Fig. 2. Algorithm of random distribution of particles and example of generated mesh

Fig. 3. RVE size effect on thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of average volume per element

Fig. 4. Thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of average volume per element and as function of heat flux axis

Fig. 5. Pseudo body centered cubic arrangement (vp = 3%)

Fig. 6. Pseudo face centered cubic arrangement ($v_p = 3\%$)

Fig. 9. Boundary conditions

Fig. 7. All particles on one face

Fig. 8. All particles between faces, in the direction of heat flux ($v_p = 3\%$)

Fig. 10. Evolution of thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of particle volume fraction

Fig. 11. Particles radius effect on thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of average volume per element

Fig. 12. Comparison between analytical models and numerical modelling as a function of particle volume fraction

Fig. 15. Comparison of thermal conductivity coefficient as a function of particle volume fraction – Hamilton model, numerical modelling and experimental results (Z600) (TOYAL)

Fig. 13. Optical microscope pictures a) Al-Z600 30%, b) Al-Z600 50%, c) Cu15%

Fig. 16. Effect of n factor on Hamilton model – Aluminium particles Z600 (TOYAL)

Fig. 14. ImageJ analysis a) Al-Z600 30%, b) Al-Z600 50%, c) Cu15%

Fig. 17. Effect of n factor on Hamilton model – Aluminium particles 11HPS (TOYAL)

Fig. 18. Effect of n factor on Hamilton model – Copper particles (Pometon)

Case	Layout	v_p (%)	λ (W/(m.K))	L (μ m)
1	Random	2.992	0.226	50
2	Pseudo body centered cubic	2.990	0.466	19.6
3	Pseudo face centered cubic	2.980	0.232	24.7
4	All particles on one face	2.978	0.223	50
5	Between faces	2.941	0.443	50

Tab. 1. Comparison between values of thermal conductivity coefficient according to particles layout

Fig. 19. Plain-weave RVE (dark part)

	ρ (g/ml)	C_p (J/(g°C))	a (mm ² /s)	λ (W/(m.K))
R12.13.03.il	1.110	1.248	0.105	0.145
Al 5%	1.185	1.204	0.145	0.207
Al 10%	1.275	1.271	0.175	0.284
Al 15%	1.363	1.267	0.218	0.376
Cu 5%	1.461	1.129	0.189	0.312
Cu 10%	1.790	0.9194	0.292	0.481
Cu 15%	2.189	0.8119	0.396	0.704
LY 556 + D230	1.12	1.217	0.140 (0.005)	0.207 (0.017)
Al - Z600 5%	1.23	1.273	0.178 (0.012)	0.270 (0.026)
Al - Z600 15%	1.38	1.117	0.270 (0.009)	0.380 (0.003)
Al - Z600 30%	1.54	1.075	0.415 (0.005)	0.597 (0.004)
Al - Z600 50%	1.77	0.9489	0.788 (0.003)	1.270 (0.042)

Tab. 2. Physical and thermal features of pure and doped resins at 23°C

Fig. 20. Distribution of heat fluxes perpendicular to lamination plane

Fig. 21. Evolution of effective transverse thermal conductivity as a function of fibre volume fraction

Resin (W/(mK))	Fibres (W/(mK))	
	Longitudinal	Transverse
0.2	600	60 or 200

Tab. 3. Values of thermal conductivity coefficients of epoxy matrix and carbon fibres